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[A proposed new method for electroencephalography trace recording in children younger than two years: an observational study](#)

Epilepsy is a common disorder in pediatric neurology, and electroencephalography (EEG) continues to play an important role in its diagnosis. However, the small size of a child's head and immaturity of the brain make EEG interpretation more difficult in children than in adults. This article presents a new method of EEG recording for children younger than 2 years designed to improve recording accuracy in children with small heads. This novel method of EEG recording, in which an increase in distance between recording electrodes is achieved without decreasing the number of electrodes or channels, compares with the traditional 10-20 system in terms of pathologic waves, artifacts, sleep spindles, and wave frequencies. Increased wave amplitude was noted with the new montages in 90 of 105 (85.7%) individuals. The calculation of wave frequency was easier and more reliable in the new montages in comparison with the prevailing recordings. More numerous sleep spindles were detected in 49 of 105 (47.6%) children. The number of detected pathological waves increased in 49 of 105 (47.6%) children on the new montages versus the 10-20 electrode system. The incidence of artifact waves in the traces was similar between the two methods in 94 (89.5%) patients and diminished in 11 of 105 (10.5%) patients. These preliminary studies suggest that the new recording system might be a suitable substitute for the routine 10-20 system, especially in young infants and neonates. Further evaluation and multicenter clinical trials will contribute to the reliability of this proposed method.

Keywords: Age Factors, Brain Waves/*physiology, Electroencephalography Epilepsy/*diagnosis/, *physiopathology, Female, Humans, Infant, Infant, Newborn, Male, Observation [Mohammad Hasanpour](#)
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